

Leachate Recirculation Using Tire Scraps – An Economical Solution for Solid Waste Management

Technical Note

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ABSTRACT

Landfilling is the most common technique used in municipal solid waste (MSW) management, In India, low laying areas in the vicinity of urban expanses are preferred for landfills. A site in Warriana area of Jalandhar district of Punjab (India) has been selected for the present study. Jalandhar is facing a big problem with solid waste management and its disposal. A total of 490-550 TPD of MSW is being generated in Jalandhar and dumped at Warriana Site. The waste when comes in contact with water produces a hazardous substance called “Leachate”. This leachate, if not isolated properly, penetrates into the ground and pollutes the groundwater. In this study, the pollution potential of the leachate present at the Warriana site has been assessed. The possible utilization of waste tire scraps and aggregates mixed in a 1:1 ratio for leachate re-circulation has been explored. A reduced pollution potential of the leachate has been observed.

Keywords: *Leachate, solid waste, tire scraps, leachate recirculation, landfill*

INTRODUCTION

Today, economical management of the MSW and the leachate generated from it has become a global challenge (USEPA 1998). Increasing population, rapid urbanization and worldwide industrialization are the major contributing factors. In the State of Punjab, most of the cities are dealing with this problem. This can be resolved by the use of various waste management alternatives such as land filling. However, authorities are facing huge difficulties to manage such an enormous amount of waste because of incorrect design, improper guidelines and lack of research in this area.

In Punjab, nearly 4500 tons of municipal solid waste is generated daily. Out of this, the 4 municipal corporations (Ludhiana, Jalandhar, Amritsar, and Patiala) account for the generation of 2000 Tons per day (TPD) of MSW in Punjab (Kaushik *et al.* 2014). Out of this, only Jalandhar

city generates about 550 TPD of MSW (Kaushik and Sethi, 2007).

Similarly, scrap tires are also another waste material which require proper collection and the disposal. Automobile tires are generally made of natural rubber elastomers, polymers and other additives. Although their composition varies with the type of the tire and the manufacturer company. Steel reinforcement are also provided in the tires to improve its strengths. These tires even after use, maintain their chemical composition. They require thousands of years to fully decompose. It has been estimated that over 200 million scrap tires are generated in India on annual basis. Only 18% of them are safely reused or recycled. Even through tires comprises only 1% of the total waste generated in India, they present significant problems due to their non-biodegradable nature. Even if we set tires on fire, they produce a lot of air pollution releasing significant amount of pollutant gases in the air.

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The use of tire scraps and aggregates would allow the leachate to drain/flow from the soil, so that it is treated and does not pollute the underlying soil and groundwater. Also, the utilization of scrap tires, would resolve the problem of their disposal. The scrap tire later purifies the leachate in the landfill and also prevents buildup of the hydraulic head within the filter. The objective of the study was to check the performance of the scrap tire-gravel mixture in treatment systems of leachate in landfills and to highlight their usefulness as a drainage medium.

STUDY AREA

The study area Jalandhar lies in Doaba region of Punjab. It is located between two rivers. The whole state is divided into 7 clusters. Jalandhar cluster contains 26 municipal committees including Municipal Corporation Jalandhar. Solid waste management in Jalandhar is under the Sanitation Department and health section department of the Municipal Corporation Jalandhar.

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Materials used in the study are as follows:

1. **Tire Scraps:** The tire chips used for this study were obtained from the material suppliers in the local market of Jalandhar city. Conventional grain size distribution analysis (ASTM: D422-63, 1998) was performed on the tire chips used in the study, due to their irregular sizes. The sizes of tire chips ranged from 25-50 mm in length, with chip size of an average of 40 mm. The test specimen comprised of wire free tire chips. The specific gravity (G_s) of tire shreds ranges from 1.032 to 1.36, depending upon amount of steel wires in the tire (Kaushik *et al.*, 2010). Reddy and Saichek (1998) found that the hydraulic conductivity of tire shreds is reduced to just 0.01 cm/second under a normal stress of 21000 psf. If the tire shreds are compressed by 65% under this level of normal stress, they met the minimum hydraulic conductivity requirement for drainage materials which is 0.001cm/s.

Fig: 1 Tire Scraps

2. The aggregates used in this study were recycled concrete aggregates (RCA). They are obtained by crushing the waste concrete cubes at the concrete laboratory of the institute. The size chosen for this study was 40 mm to 20 mm.

Fig: 2 Recycled Aggregates

Experimental Setup: In order to create conditions like the landfill, a 12-inch pipe was taken with its one end closed and the other end open. A tap was also attached to the bottom of the pipe for the extraction of the leachate. The RCA and tire scraps were laid in layers, keeping each layer approximately 4 to 5 inches thick. The leachate which has been obtained from the Warriana site is recirculated several times and its properties are checked after every 10 cycles for upto 30 cycles. The various parameters for which the leachate was tested were:

- BOD (Bio-Chemical Oxygen Demand)
- COD (Chemical Oxygen Demand)
- Chlorides
- Hardness
- Acidity
- Total Solids
- Total Suspended Solids

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The leachate sample was taken from the Warriana site. Then it was tested initially and after particular no. of cycles. During this, the reduction in the BOD and the COD values of the leachate was observed. The improvement observed in the quality of the leachate from its initial stage to up to 30 cycles from the filter media have been presented in Figure 1 to 4.

Fig.1: BOD observed till 30 Cycles

Fig.2: COD observed till 30 Cycles

Fig.3: Chlorides observed till 30 Cycles

Fig.4: Acidity observed till 30 Cycles

Table 1: Change in pollution potential of leachate after passing through 30 cycles

Parameter	Results of initial leachate	Results after 30 cycles	Observations
Biochemical oxygen demand (BOD)	180 mg/l	115 mg/l	2.77% decrease in the value of BOD
Chemical oxygen demand (COD)	11.2 mg/l	3.2 mg/l	26.78 % decrease in the value of COD
Chloride	464.85 mg/l	204.93 mg/l	36.56 % decrease in the value of chloride
Acidity	66 mg/l	18 mg/l	66.66 % decrease in the value of acidity
Hardness	940 mg/l	610 mg/l	17.02 % decrease in the value of hardness
Total solids	292 mg/l	10 mg/l	68.15 % decrease in the values of total solids
Total suspended solids	17 mg/l	1.0 mg/l	70.58 % decrease in the values of total suspended solids

CONCLUSION

The leachate collected from Warriana dumping site of Jalandhar has been characterized for different parameters such as Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD), Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD), Hardness, Chlorides, Sulfates, Total solids and dissolved solids to check its potential to pollute the underground aquifers. It was analyzed that leachate from this site is of moderate strength and requires some treatment before its safe disposal either on land surface or in water bodies. For this the leachate has been passed through the layers of gravel and tire chips.

After passing the leachate by 30 cycles the pollution potential measured as BOD is reduced by 36.11%, COD is reduced by 72%, Chloride is reduced by 56%, acidity is reduced by 73%, Hardness is reduced by 36%, total solids are reduced by 97 % and total suspended solids are reduced by 95%. The analysis shows that the tire scraps and RCA can be beneficially reused to reduce the pollution problems arising from the landfill. The approach used in this study can be used for other landfill sites to reduce pollution potential of the leachate.

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